

УДК 630.377.22

CALCULATION OF TENSION FORCE OF TRACTION LOAD-LIFTING CABLE OF SUSPENDED CABLE TIMBER TRANSPORTING SYSTEM

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Introduction. A considerable part of Ukrainian forest fund is located in the Carpathians. Cable timber transporting systems are economically reasonable and the most environmentally thrifty means of primary transportation of timber in mountainous and inaccessible areas. The improvement of important units construction and the development of new schemes of cable timber transporting systems is the main scientific and practical task, the implementation of which requires the creation of new and improvement of existing calculation methods.

Exposition of a subject matter. In order to study the internal loads arising in the drive links and other structural units of cable timber transporting system, it is necessary to take into account the size and actual nature of external technological efforts, particularly, tension force of traction load-lifting cable.

Typical technological cycle of cable systems operation contains 4 main stages, lasting respectively t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4 :

- Selection of cable weaknesses with gradual increase in tension force of cable to the value of weight of the load;
- Load lifting ;
- Locking of load with cargo carriage;
- Movement of cargo carriage with load along the bearing cable.

Apart from the above-mentioned stages, the additional ones are possible, such as: movement of empty load handling devices and pulling timber from the side to the line of bearing cable.

The dependences for determination of tension force of traction load-lifting cable $S(t)$ and the duration of each stage of the technological cycle have been established:

$$S(t) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0 \leq t \leq \frac{Q[L - x_K(t_0)]}{C_K \cdot v} \Rightarrow S_0(t) = \frac{C_K \cdot v}{L - x_K(t_0)} \cdot t \\ \frac{Q[L - x_K(t_0)]}{C_K \cdot v} < t \leq \frac{1}{v} \left(\frac{Q[L - x_K(t_0)]}{C_K} + H_G \right) \Rightarrow S_1(t) \\ \left[\frac{1}{v} \left(\frac{Q[L - x_K(t_0)]}{C_K} + H_G \right) < t \leq \frac{1}{v} \left(\frac{Q[L - x_K(t_0)]}{C_K} + H_G \right) + t_c \right] \Rightarrow S_2(t) \\ \left. \begin{array}{l} t > \frac{1}{v} \left(\frac{Q[L - x_K(t_0)]}{C_K} + H_G \right) + t_c \\ t \leq \frac{1}{v} \left(\frac{Q[L - x_K(t_0)]}{C_K} + H_G + \frac{L - x_K(t_0)}{\cos \beta} + \frac{(gq_K)^2 \cdot (L - x_K(t_0))^3}{24 \cdot H^2} \cos \beta \right) + t_c \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow S_3(t) \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

where $S_0(t), S_1(t), S_2(t), S_3(t)$ – tension force of traction load-lifting cable respectively when choosing cable weaknesses, lifting load, locking of load with cargo carriage and transporting a cargo carriage along the bearing cable [2, 3]; Q – weight of load; $x_K(t_0)$ – coordinate of cargo carriage at the initial time t_0 ; H_G – height of load lifting; v – velocity of winding of rope onto the drum; β – inclination angle of the chord of span to the horizon; C_K – longitudinal stiffness of

traction lifting cable; H – horizontal component of tension force of cable [2, 3]; t_c – time of load locking [2]; L – span length; q_k – linear cable mass.

An example of calculation based on the proposed dependencies for cable timber transporting system, with carrying capacity of 16 κH and span length of 400 m, is shown in figure. 1.

Figure 1 – Temporal dependence of tension force in the traction load-lifting cable

Conclusions. It is established that the maximal short-term effort in traction load-lifting cable occurs at the moment of locking of load with the carriage. The obtained dependences, along with corresponding software, are necessary for mathematical modeling of dynamic oscillatory processes in the elements of cable timber transporting systems and substantiation of the choice of their basic constructional parameters and safe regimes of operation.

References

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